

Inductive Effect of *ortho*- and *para*-Substituents in 3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidinones as indicated by their Reaction Rates with *N*-Bromosuccinimide

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There is considerable difference in the reactivities of 2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one, 3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one and 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one towards oxidation¹. In 3,5-dimethylpiperidin-4-one, the decreased non-bonded *gauche*-interactions between enolic OH and CH₃ groups, which is possible only in highly distorted chair or twist conformation, makes it least reactive². The study of rates of oxidation of 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones with substituents in *ortho*- and *para*-positions of the phenyl rings is considered to be of special interest because it would exemplify the inductive effect of the substituent on the reactivity. Hence, with a view to focus on the structure-reactivity correlation we have selected seven 3,5-dimethyl-2,6-diarylpeperidin-4-ones (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

The result of the kinetic study indicates that 1 mole of NBS reacted with 1 mole of piperidinone to afford α -ketol. The product was characterised by tic

and ir and nmr spectral studies. Under the experimental conditions [NBS] $\ll$ [piperidinone], the plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time were linear indicating the order in [NBS] to be unity. The rate increased with increase in [piperidinone]. The plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log$ [piperidinone] was linear with unit slope indicating first order dependence in [piperidinone]. A four-fold change in

[Hg(OAc)₂] ($0.5-2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³) had negligible effect on the rate of oxidation. Added succinimide in the range of $1.0-3.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ had a negligible retarding effect. The reaction was carried out at four different temperatures in the range 298–323 K and the activation parameters were computed using Arrhenius equation. The negative entropy of activation is consistent with the less mobile cyclic transition state in the rate-limiting step. The isokinetic temperature (357.6 K) obtained from Exner plot is found to be greater than the experimental temperature (308 K) (Table 1). No induced polymerisation with methyl methacrylate was observed.

Mechanism : The observed first order dependence on [NBS] as well as [piperidinone] is suggestive of a mechanism shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law,

$$-\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = K_{\text{c}q} k [\text{NBS}] [\text{piperidinone}]$$

which is in accord with the observation. The negligible effects observed by varying the concentration of mercury(II) acetate and the concentration of succinimide indicate NBS molecule as the active oxidising species³. NBS, a two-electron oxidant, preferably attacks the enol form of the piperidinone⁴ in the rate-determining step forming a cyclic transition state which decomposes to α -bromo compound. This undergoes fast nucleophilic solvolysis to yield α -ketol as the main product.

Substituent effect : Introduction of electron-releasing and electron-attracting groups in *ortho*- and *para*-positions of the phenyl rings in the least reactive 3,5-

TABLE I-RATE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

[P] = 1.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, [NaOAc] = 5.0 $\times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, [NBS] = 1.0 $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.0 $\times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, HOAc = 80% (v/v)

Compd.	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	k_2^+ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diphenyl-4-piperidinone	81.0	78.4	85.2	-22.1	2.27
3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-di- <i>o</i> -tolyl-4-piperidinone	85.8	83.2	85.5	-7.5	2.02
3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-di- <i>p</i> -tolyl-4-piperidinone	89.8	87.2	85.6	5.4	1.98
3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-di- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-4-piperidinone	77.9	75.4	82.9	-24.5	5.60
3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-di- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-4-piperidinone	84.8	82.3	84.1	-5.9	3.53
3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-di- <i>p</i> -anisyl-4-piperidinone	60.7	58.1	82.8	-80.2	5.80
3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-di- <i>o</i> -nitrophenyl-4-piperidinone	73.7	71.2	83.5	-4.0	4.40

*At 308 K.

Scheme 1

dimethyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one existing in a non-chair conformation⁵ opens the way to a deeper understanding of structure-reactivity correlation in this oxidation kinetics. The sequence of reactivity observed

(Table 1) is (i) *p*-OCH₃ > *p*-Cl > *p*-H > *p*-CH₃ and (ii) *o*-Cl > *o*-NO₂ > *o*-H > *o*-CH₃. Inductive effect offers a very simple explanation accounting for the above sequence. The electron-releasing groups decrease the rate of oxidation while electron-attracting ones enhance it. This is in accordance with the fact that electron-withdrawing groups facilitate the formation of cyclic transition state in the rate-determining step. A slight deviation of reactivity is observed in *o*-NO₂ compound. The unexpected fast rate for *p*-methoxy may be due to the activation of the aromatic nucleus and hence ring-bromination as a side-reaction. But it is difficult to furnish positive evidence for the existence of ring-brominated products in a very fast reaction by isolation or otherwise.

The conclusion made about the inductive effect the present study is only a possibility and final conclusion can be drawn only from a study on the *meta*-substituted derivatives. As our study was limited to *para*- and *ortho*-substituted compounds, we have not attempted to prepare and subject the *meta*-substituted

compounds to the kinetic study.

Experimental

Acetic acid (ExceleR, Qualigens), *N*-bromosuccinimide (G.R., Loba Chemie) and reagent grade sodium acetate and mercury(II) acetate were used. 3,5-Dimethyl-2,6-diarylpiperidin-4-ones were prepared by reported method⁶. Solutions of NBS in aqueous 80% (v/v) acetic acid were always prepared fresh in black-coated flasks and their strengths checked iodometrically. For kinetic measurements, piperidone (0.005 mol), mercury(II) acetate (2.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³) and sodium acetate (5.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³) in aqueous 80% (v/v) acetic acid and NBS (0.012 mol) solution were separately equilibrated in black-coated bottles. The reaction was started by adding NBS to piperidone solution and the rate was measured by determining unconsumed NBS iodometrically at different intervals of time. Pseudo-first order condition was maintained by taking [piperidone] $\gg$ [NBS]. The rate constants were computed by the method of least-squares and found in duplicate runs to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

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